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Rare Earth Complexes with N, O-Donor Ligands—Part II. Complexes of Gd(III), Tb(III), Dy(III) and Ho(III) with 2-(2'-Hydroxyphenyl)benzimidazole

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IN a previous communication¹, we described the 8-coordinated complexes of the type $[M(\text{HO-PhBzH})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2]\text{NO}_3 \cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$ where HO-PhBzH stands for the title ligand and M is Y(III), La(III), Ce(III), Pr(III), Nd(III) or Sm(III). We report here similar complexes with Gd(III), Tb(III) Dy(III) and Ho(III).

The nitrates of these middle rare earth elements (procured as hydrated crystals from Indian Rare Earths Ltd., Kerala, in 99.9-99.99% purity), when interacted with HO-PhBzH in 1 : 2 molar proportions in refluxing ethyl acetate, yield pale yellow 8-coordinate complexes of the type $[M(\text{HO-PhBzH})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2]\text{NO}_3 \cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in solid state. The 1 : 1 electrolyte nature of the complexes is supported by their molar conductance values** lying in the range 117-128 ohm⁻¹ cm² in DMF. The water of crystallisation is lost by heating upto 120° and no further loss is recorded upto 180°.

The room-temperature magnetic moment values are in good agreement with the values calculated on the formula², $\mu_{\text{eff}} = g[J(J+1)]^{\frac{1}{2}}$ and confirm the terpositive state of the metals in these complexes.

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** All physical measurements were made as described in Ref. 1.

Infrared spectra: The existence of both coordinated (C_{2v}) and uncoordinated (D_{3h}) nitrate groups are inferred from the ir spectra of the complexes.

Of the six fundamentals expected³ for a coordinated nitrate, five are exhibited by Gd-, Tb- and Ho-complexes, whereas four by the Dy-complex. The $\nu_4(B_1)$ mode appears as a triplet (1470, 1462, 1455 cm⁻¹) in each complex and $\nu_1(A_1)$ appears as a doublet (Gd, Tb : 1300, 1288 cm⁻¹) or a singlet (Dy : 1295 ; Ho : 1298 cm⁻¹). The $\nu_2(A_1)$ mode which appears at 1022 cm⁻¹ in Gd-, Tb- and Ho-complexes is obscured in the Dy-complex. The weak bands at 800 cm⁻¹ and 700 cm⁻¹ (Gd, Tb : 700 ; Dy : 695 ; Ho : 698 cm⁻¹) are assigned to the $\nu_5(B_2)$ and $\nu_6(B_1)$ modes respectively. On arguments mentioned earlier¹, we treat the coordinated nitrate ions as bidentate groups in these complexes also, supported by the magnitude⁴ of $\nu_4 - \nu_1$ (~170 cm⁻¹).

The presence of uncoordinated nitrate⁵ is substantiated by appearance of shoulders at 1350 cm⁻¹ ascribed to $\nu_3(E')$ mode and at 850 cm⁻¹ ascribed to $\nu_3(A'')$ mode uniformly in each complex.

The assignment of bands for $\nu_{(OH)}$ and $\nu_{(NH)}$ have been discussed in detail in our previous paper¹. In accordance with that, the strong broad band at 3200 cm⁻¹ is assigned to $\nu_{(OH)}$ and a shoulder at 3060-3050 cm⁻¹ to $\nu_{(NH)}$ in each complex. The $\delta_{(HOH)}$ is exhibited¹ at 1642 cm⁻¹ as a weak band on account of water of crystallisation of the complexes. Extra bands in the 3 μ region at 3525 cm⁻¹ in the Tb- and Ho-complexes indicate the presence of non-hydrogen bonded OH groups also.

Electronic spectra: The spectra of Tb(III)-, Dy(III)- and Ho(III)-complexes have been recorded in DMF and assignment of bands made with reference to the levels of the metal ions in LaCl₃-host.

As the first excited level (⁶P) of Gd(III) lies 32000 cm⁻¹ above the ground term (⁸S_{7/2}), all bands of the metal ion are expected to be in the ultraviolet region. Because of intense ligand bands appearing in this region, the spectrum of Gd(III)-complex could not be studied.

The bands due to transitions, ⁷F₆ → ⁷F₃ (4.34 kK) and ⁷F₆ → ⁷F₂ (4.95, 5.06 kK) of Tb(III) in the given complex show little red-shifts from the LaCl₃-host reference⁵. However, the ⁷F₆ → ⁷F₁ (5.19, 5.37 kK), ⁷F₆ → ⁷F₀ (5.52 kK) and ⁷F₆ → ⁵D₃ (25.64 kK) bands suffer 2-4% red-shifts with reference to the same.

The two hypersensitive bands due to ⁶H_{15/2} → ⁶H_{9/2} and ⁶H_{15/2} → ⁶F_{11/2} transitions of Dy(III) appear to have mixed up at 7.72 kK in the given complex. Similarly, ⁶H_{15/2} → ⁶H_{7/2} and ⁶H_{15/2} → ⁶F_{9/2} give rise to a single band at 5.03 kK. The transitions from ⁶H_{15/2} to other levels, ⁶H_{5/2} (10.20 kK), ⁶F_{7/2} (11.00 kK), ⁶F_{5/2} (12.35 kK) and ⁶F_{3/2} (13.16 kK) also appear almost at the same positions as they do in LaCl₃-host⁶.

TABLE—CHARACTERISATION DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Complex	%M	%N	%loss in wt. at 120°	Cond.*	μ_{eff} in B.M. (Temp.)
[Gd(HO-PhBzH) ₂ (NO ₂) ₂]NO ₃ ·2H ₂ O	C 19.67	12.26	4.50	128	8.07(306.5°K)
	F 19.38	12.40	4.82		
[Tb(HO-PhBzH) ₂ (NO ₂) ₂]NO ₃ ·2H ₂ O	C 19.85	12.23	4.49	125	9.46(306.5°K)
	F 19.69	12.44	5.06		
[Dy(HO-PhBzH) ₂ (NO ₂) ₂]NO ₃ ·1.5H ₂ O	C 20.42	12.32	3.39	118	10.73(307.5°K)
	F 20.35	12.41	3.62		
[Ho(HO-PhBzH) ₂ (NO ₂) ₂]NO ₃ ·H ₂ O	C 20.90	12.42	2.28	117	10.55(306.5°K)
	F 20.73	12.63	2.45		

HO-PhBzH=C₁₁H₁₀N₂O

* Electrical conductance in ohm⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹ in DMF at 305°K

C=Calcd. ; F=Found.

The bands identified as due to transitions from the ⁵I₈ ground level to ⁵I₆ (8.55, 8.68 kK), ⁵I₅ (11.28 kK), ⁵F₆ (15.27, 15.43 kK), ⁵F₄ (18.62 kK), ⁵F₃ (20.66 kK), ³K₃ (21.28 kK) and ⁵G₆ (or ⁵F₁; 22.12 kK) levels of Ho(III) in the present complex suffer practically no shift from positions in LaCl₃-host⁷.

The general trend suggests that the extent of covalency decreases with increasing number of electrons in the *f*-orbital.

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Complexes of Pd(II) with Thiohydrazone Derivatives

Derivatives

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THE complexes of some acet-thiohydrazides and acet-thiohydrazones with Ni(II) are known¹⁻⁴.

In previous communication, complexes of oxovanadium(IV) with some thiohydrazone derivatives have been reported⁵. In the present note, preparation and characterisation of complexes of Pd(II) with acet-thiohydrazides namely, phenylthiohydrazone (pthH), *p*-anisidylthiohydrazone (athH), furfurylthiohydrazone (fthH), *o*-hydroxyphenylthiohydrazone (*o*-hthH) and *p*-hydroxyphenylthiohydrazone (*p*-hthH) are reported.

Experimental

The ligands were prepared as reported in the literature⁶. Palladium(II) chloride was obtained from Johnson and Mathey Ltd. The complexes PdL₂ (L=deprotonated ligands) were prepared by the following general method: an aqueous PdCl₂ solution (0.2 g in 100 ml; pH~2) was treated with a 2% ethanolic solution of the ligand in requisite proportion when a cream yellow complex separated immediately. The product was digested on a steam bath for about 20 min, filtered, washed with aqueous ethanol and dried in an air oven between 80 and 90°.

The results of elemental analysis and important ir bands are recorded in Table 1. The palladium(II) was estimated as dimethylglyoximate after decomposing the complex with conc. HNO₃ and perchloric acid. Physical measurements were done as reported earlier⁵.

Results and Discussion

Thiohydrazides (A) has been found to coordinate as monoanionic ligand in thiol tautomer (B) with Pd(II) in neutral,

(R=phenyl-, *p*-anisidyl-, furfuryl-, *o*-hydroxyphenyl- and *p*-hydroxyphenyl groups).

alkaline and even acidic medium forming *bis* chelated neutral complexes PdL₂ (LH=pthH, athH, fthH, *o*-hthH or *p*-hthH). Excepting *p*-hydroxyphenylthiohydrazone complex [Pd(*p*-hth)₂], other *bis* chelates are separated out almost quantitatively from aqueous or aqueous ethanolic medium. The complex [Pd(*p*-hth)₂] is slightly soluble in water but dissolves appreciably in ethanol, methanol etc. whereas other *bis* chelates are almost insoluble in water as well as organic solvents like methanol, ethanol and benzene. Almost all the complexes are fairly soluble in DMF. The complexes are diamagnetic supporting their planar stereochemistry with